

MINING USER NAVIGATION PATTERNS FOR EFFICIENT RELEVANCE FEEDBACK FOR CBIR

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ABSTRACT:

In today's modernized world, content based image retrieval (CBIR) is considered as a bastion in image retrieval system. For making CBIR most suitable and productive technique, relevance feedback technique is used in conjunction with CBIR for producing more specific results which are obtained by taking feedback from user. However, existing relevance feedback-based CBIR methods usually request a number of iterative feedbacks for production of best search results, particularly in huge database. But this seems of no use in real world applications. In this paper, we propose a novel method, NRPf (Navigation pattern based relevance feedback method) is used for enhancing effectiveness and efficiency in CBIR while copying large image data. In terms of efficiency, the iterations of feedback will get reduced drastically reduced substantially by using the navigation patterns discovered from the user query log. Effectiveness of our proposed search algorithm NRPf Search makes use of the discovered navigation patterns. It also produces query refinement strategies in other kinds, Query Point Movement (QPM), Query Expansion (QEX) and Query Reweighting (QR), to converge the search space toward user's intention effectively. For this purpose NRPf systems are used in increasing quality of retrieved image. The experimental shows NRPf outperforms other established methods considerably in terms of precision, coverage and number of feedbacks.

KEYWORDS: Content based image retrieval, relevance feedback, query point movement, query expansion, navigation pattern mining etc.

INTRODUCTION:

Multimedia contents are growing explosively and the need for multimedia retrieval is occurring more and more frequently in our daily life. Understanding the image has become difficult but that has raised the interest in this domain. Extracting valuable knowledge from a large-scale multimedia repository, so-called multimedia mining, has been studied by few researchers.

Typically, in the development of an image requisition system, semantic image retrieval relies heavily on the related captions, categories, file-names, and other manual descriptions or annotated keywords. Unfortunately, this kind of manual-based image retrieval suffers from two problems: high-priced manual annotation and inappropriate automated annotation.

PROPOSED SYSTEM:

The proposed algorithm NRPf Search performs the navigation-pattern-based search to match the user's intention by merging three query refinement strategies. As a result, additional problems such as visual diversity and exploration-convergence are solved. For navigation-pattern-based search, the hierarchical BFS based KNN is employed to narrow the gap between visual features and human concepts effectively. In addition, the involved methods for special data partition and pattern pruning also speed up the image exploration. The experimental results reveal that the proposed approach NRPf is very effective in terms of precision and coverage. With short term relevance feedback, the navigation system algorithm will help in assisting the users in obtaining the best results. Moreover, the new search algorithm NRPf Search can bring out more accurate results than other well-known approaches.

Fig. No.1. Example of navigation pattern trees [18]

WORKING OF THE NRPf METHOD:

INITIAL QUERY PROCESSING PHASE:

Without considering the feature weight, this phase extracts the visual features from the original

query image to find the similar images. Afterward, the good examples (also called positive examples in this paper) picked up by the user are further analyzed at the first feedback (also called iteration 0 in this paper).

IMAGE SEARCH PHASE:

Behind the search phase, our intent is to extend the one search point to multiple search points by integrating the navigation patterns and the proposed search algorithm NPRF Search. Thus, the varied inclusion of the user's interest can be successfully implied. In this phase, a new query point at each feedback is generated by the preceding positive examples. Then, the k-nearest images to the new query point can be found by expanding the weighted query. The search procedure does not stop unless the user is satisfied with the retrieval results

Fig.no.1 Work flow of NPRF method

KNOWLEDGE DISCOVERY PHASE:

Learning from users' behaviors in image retrieval can be viewed as one type of knowledge discovery. Consequently, this paper primarily concerns the construction of a navigation model by discovering the implicit navigation patterns from users' browsing behaviors. This navigation model can provide image search with a good support to predict optimal image browsing paths.

DATA STORAGE PHASE:

The databases in this phase can be regarded as the knowledge marts of a knowledge warehouse, which store integrated, time-variant, and nonvolatile collection of useful data including images, navigation patterns, log files, and image features. The knowledge warehouse is very helpful to improve the quality of image retrieval.

Note that the procedure of constructing rule base from the image databases can be conducted periodically to maintain the validity of the proposed approach.

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS:

HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS:

- System : Pentium IV 2.4 GHz.
- Hard Disk : 40 GB.
- Monitor : 15 VGA Color.
- Mouse : Logitech.
- Ram : 512 MB.

SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS:

- Operating System : Windows xp , Linux
- Language : Java 1.4 or more
- Technology : SWT, SWT

CONCLUSION:

The major difference between our proposed approach and other contemporary approaches is that we approximate an optimal solution to resolve the problems existing in current IR such as redundant browsing and exploration convergence. To this end, the approximated solution takes advantage of exploited knowledge (navigation patterns) to assist the proposed search strategy in efficiently hunting the desired images.

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